

AN EXPLORATORY REVIEW ON ENERGY EFFICIENT TECHNIQUES FOR DC DRIVE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

We contemplate vitality stockpiling gear that is associated with DC6 chopper of diesel train (WDM2) of railroad. We take reference model of diesel train WDM2 for the investigation of paper. Amid the driving time frame, the speeding up of the prepare gets to be distinctly bigger because of the boosting operation of the hardware. The gear charges a piece of recovered vitality when it supports the voltage amid braking period, and releases the put away vitality when it used to work other electrical hardware. At the season of regenerative braking we store the electrical vitality it is help to spare the vitality. In this paper, we chose battery bank for the vitality stockpiling gadget of the gear.

I. INTRODUCTION

The expansion of the particular power request by present day railroad footing vehicles suggests to discover solid specialized arrangement so as to decrease the vitality utilization. The run of the mill travel i.e. of metro trains, light rail vehicles (cable car) is made of increasing speeds, drifting and braking periods. Specifically, the biggest part of the vitality drawn by the prepare is credited to the speeding up and braking due to the diminished separation between two ensuing stations. Present day electrical drives for footing engines advantage from the likelihood of regenerative braking and the points of interest identified with the sparing of vitality endeavoring to infuse the vitality into the providing line.

DC arrangement engines have been utilized customarily in footing applications, regenerative braking has not frequently been utilized as a part of ordinary footing gear previously. The fundamental purpose behind this is an arrangement energized generator is flimsy when working into a settled voltage supply. In this manner, for running on the footing supply, a different excitation is required. Such a course of action, in any case, is extremely delicate to supply voltage changes, and a quick element reaction is required to give a sufficient brake control. Nonetheless, the utilizations of a DC chopper permit the regenerative braking of DC arrangement engines because of its quick element reaction. By and by, the chopper must adapt to the transient conditions and ought to be fitted with a quick acting shut circle controller. This is important to congratulate the required execution qualities in the relentless state and transient conditions. Before study, investigation and recreation of chopper circuit with the office of regenerative braking, the motoring and in addition braking attributes of a DC engine should be assessed to decide the points of confinement of braking pace and the control in order to take after inside the requirements of the most extreme braking force and current. Once the underlying stage is finished, a model of the drive execution in MATLAB is conceived to be made with a specific end goal to examine and to decide the regenerative attributes under beat control conditions.[9]

II. TWO QUADRANT CHOPPER

A chopper is a static power electronic gadget that believers settled dc input voltage to a variable dc yield voltage. A Chopper might be considered as dc likeness an air conditioner transformer since they act in an indistinguishable way. As chopper includes one phase change, these are more productive [2]. Choppers are currently being utilized everywhere throughout the world for quick travel frameworks. These are likewise utilized as a part of trolley autos, marine crane, forklift trucks and mine haulers. The future electric vehicles are probably going to utilize choppers for their speed control and braking. Chopper frameworks offer smooth control, high effectiveness, quicker reaction and recovery office [2]. The power semiconductor gadgets utilized for a chopper circuit can be compel commutated thyristor, control BJT, MOSFET and

IGBT.GTO based chopper are likewise utilized. These gadgets are for the most part spoken to by a switch. At the point when the turn is off, no current can stream. Current courses through the heap when switch is "on". The power semiconductor gadgets have on-state voltage drop of 0.5V to 2.5V crosswise over them. For effortlessness, this voltage drop over these gadgets is for the most part disregarded [2]. As specified over, a chopper is dc proportional to an air conditioner transformer, have ceaselessly factor turn's proportion. Like a transformer, a chopper can be utilized to venture down or venture up the settled dc input voltage. [1][6]

Chopper is ordinarily isolated into four sorts: venture down chopper, venture up chopper, two-quadrant chopper and four-quadrant chopper. Two-quadrant chopper would be utilized as a part of the exploration. It is fundamentally blend of venture down and venture up chopper. It is worked in two method of operation venture down chopper. At the point when current is streaming back to the supply (negative), it goes about as a stage up chopper.[10]

In the research, two-quadrant dc to dc converter will be used. The configuration of basic dc to dc converter is shown below

Fig1: Circuit configuration of two-quadrant chopper

There are two switches S1 and S2 associated over a dc voltage source ES. The switches open and close on the other hand in a manner that when S1 is shut, S2 is open and the other way around. S1 and S2 turn on time add to one time of exchanging. Diode associated parallel with the switch would hinder the current to stream descending however gave streaming upward. IGBT and diode associated in parallel can be rearranged and spoken to as a solitary bidirectional perfect switch. IGBT gives the current to stream descending while diode gives the current to stream upward. Turn on voltage for diode is sufficiently little to be ignored. Henceforth, a bidirectional perfect change was demonstrated IGBT and diode in parallel. The two switch utilized as a part of two-quadrant chopper were controlled by a gating signal supply to the switch. This gating sign is either on or off in a periodical way. To fill this need, beat generator piece was utilized. Since the two switches were turned on the other hand. It is more productive to utilize just a single gating circuit, implies one heartbeat generator. An inverter was intended to modify the gating signal provided for second switch. [12][25]

III. REGENERATIVE BRAKING

Operation in quadrants II and IV compares to forward and turn around braking, separately. For the DC models of the Electric Drives library, this braking is regenerative, implying that the dynamic vitality of the engine stack framework is changed over to electric vitality and came back to the power source. This bidirectional power stream is acquired by reversing the engine's associations when the current gets to be distinctly invalid (DC1 and DC3) or by the utilization of a moment converter (DC2 and DC4). Both techniques permit upsetting the engine current with a specific end goal to make an electric torque inverse to the heading of movement. The chopper-sustained DC drive models (DC5, DC6, and DC7) deliver regenerative braking in comparable styles.

The fundamental guideline of regenerative braking in DC chopper drives is clarified in figure 2, which portrays chopper and the engine comparable circuit. Figure 3 shows the rearranged proportionate circuits of regenerative braking for investigation. On shutting the chopper switch the present ascents because of a virtual short out that is made over the machine terminals. The vitality in this way put away in the engine armature because of idleness is permitted to build up the present as appeared in figure 3(a). This present makes vitality put away in the inductance. As and when the chopper switch is opened as portrayed in figure 3(b), this vitality is next exchanged to the DC mains supply. This happens gave the supply is open.

Fig 2: Principle of Regenerative Braking

The equivalent circuits of DC motor now working as a generator, in the regenerative mode of operation is shown in figures 2(a) and (b) for duty and freewheeling intervals of operation. Further, figure 2(c) gives the waveform of current and voltage during this mode of machine operation. Since average voltage is zero, therefore, we have the following steady-state equation:

Fig 3:- Equivalent Circuit and waveforms of current and voltage

$$V_d (1 - K_d) = K_b \omega_n - I_{av} R_a \quad (1)$$

$$\omega_n = \frac{V_d (1 - K_d) + I_{av} R_a}{K_b} \quad (2)$$

$$i_d(t = 0) = I_f$$

$$\& i_d(t = k_d \cdot T) = I_d$$

$$K_b \omega_n = i_d R_a + L_a \frac{di_d}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Solving and obtaining the value of i_d as;

$$K_b \omega_n = V_{dc} + i_f R_a + L_a \frac{di_d}{dt} \quad (4)$$

$$i_d = I_f \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_a}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_a}} \right) \frac{K_b \omega_n}{R_a} \quad (5)$$

For the off interval with i_d (at $t = k_d \cdot T$) = I_d , & $i_d(t = 0) = I_f$ We obtain after solving equation (5):

$$I_f = I_d \cdot e^{-\frac{k_d T}{k_d \tau_a}} + \left(1 - e^{-\frac{k_d T}{\tau_a}} \right) \left(\frac{K_b \omega_n - V_{dc}}{R_a} \right) \quad (6)$$

Proceeding in the similar manner as before, for the solutions I_d and I_f are obtained as under;

$$I_d = \frac{E_b - V_{dc}}{R_a} \left\{ \left(1 - e^{-\frac{(1-k_d)T}{\tau_a}} \right) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{(1-k_d)T}{\tau_a}} \right) \right\} \quad (7)$$

$$I_f = \frac{E_b - V_{dc}}{R_a} \left\{ e^{-\frac{k_d T}{\tau_a}} - e^{-\frac{T}{\tau_a}} \right\} 1 - e^{-\frac{T}{\tau_a}} \quad (8)$$

Substituting the contents of (4) into equation (5) & simplifying we get the ripple factor γ ;
Now the ripple factor

$$\gamma = \frac{I_d - I_f}{2I_w} \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{V_d}{2I_w R_a} \left\{ \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{(1-k_d)T}{\tau_a}} - e^{-\frac{k_d T}{\tau_a}} + e^{-\frac{T}{\tau_a}}}{1 - e^{-\frac{k_d T}{\tau_a}}} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Condition (10) is inferred to give the swell substance in the armature current of energized DC engine in the observing and recovering methods of the drive. Note that the numerical expressions determined and created in this segment are substantial for ceaseless conduction of current through the armature. The throbbing way of current waveform amid these methods of the DC drives operation. In any case, if the engine is completely stacked the inductance of the armature winding and that of the field winding are by and sufficiently large to do the characteristic smoothing of armature and field current waveforms. [14][17][24]

IV. SIMULINK EXPERIMENT MODEL

Matlab/Simulink form 7 R2007b is being utilized as an apparatus for reenactment .For recreation purposes set up of OHP link a 25KV power supply is utilized. Well known two quadrant chopper demonstrate DC6 is utilized to study typical and braking modes. The battery bank is considered as 72V 100Ah. To change over between battery bank and principle control supply current course is taken as criticism. At the switch bearing of current a contactor is worked consequently that diverts the braking produced EMF to the battery bank. Encourage a charging control framework can be utilized to direct the current being provided to the battery bank. What's more, that will likewise deal with cheating and profound release. On ordinary run i.e. on first quadrant operation framework works typically in motoring mode. Speed and torque qualities are taken as factors that speak to motor speed and torque. Contingent upon postulations values chopper exchanging heartbeats are produced. [3][5][19]

Fig 4: Block diagram of simulation model

V. RESULT

Investigation of WDM2 diesel train motor is accomplished for the premise of our model. it is found that warmth misfortune happening in the resistance utilized as a part of regenerative braking can be used for other electrical gadget and furthermore to charge battery banks and ultra capacitor along these lines a gigantic measure of influence can be spared . Facilitate this put away vitality in battery banks can be exchanged to other joined boogies

VI. CONCLUSION

By the utilization of these procedures we spare a lot of vitality which is squandered on the season of regenerative braking. Same review with some particular changes can be utilized for half and half electric vehicle and different trains also. Set up of battery bank, ultra capacitor can be utilized.

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